

Probabilistic $\exp(ipx)$ /Momentum and Deterministic t /Energy in Reflection/Refraction

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In Newtonian mechanics a particle with constant momentum moves deterministically according to $x=p/m t$. Even a quantum object such as a photon or electron should satisfy this equation on average to give meaning to the notion of the speed of light in a vacuum, for example. Thus it seems surprising that a quantum free particle is also associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which only contains momentum and is periodic and complex. Furthermore the physical consequences of $\exp(ipx)$ are real as shown in a two-slit interference experiment etc. In this note, we attempt to discover why $\exp(ipx)$ exists in the first place by examining the example of the reflection/refraction of light which occurs in the macroscopic classical world.

Basically our argument is based on analyzing two important pieces of information in the system, namely the scalar energy (or particle count) and the vector momentum. A main point we make is that energy or particle number considerations are linked to determinism i.e. a specific time of interaction. One may note that the interaction x is fixed by the two medium barrier. This means a single incident photon exists in one time range and the reflected OR refracted photon in another. It is possible to compare the incident photon to either the reflected or refracted or to a sum of probabilities. In particular, a single photon has an energy E and a count of 1. If it reflects, it has an energy E and count of 1 so there is a balance, likewise for refraction. Thinking in terms of probabilities “ a ” and $1-a$ to reflect/refract: $1= a + 1-a$.

Can one perform such a matching for momentum, which is a physical piece of information? We argue one cannot. For example, a single incident photon has a momentum p which is linked to the impulse it may deliver. If it refracts, “all of a sudden” it is linked with momentum of $p_2 = n_2 p$ where n_2 is the index of refraction in the second medium and $n_1=1$. This seems problematic because a physical impulse of $2p$ is all of a sudden an impulse of $2p_2$. Thus there exists a big problem which seems to require the notion of probability and all three momentum values p , $-p$ and p_2 considered together, unlike the situation of energy/particle number for which a comparison of the incident photon and one possible result yields a balance.

Combining all three momenta, however, is also problematic in a deterministic picture because the incident photon exists in one time range and the reflected or refracted in another. How can one possibly compare them together? The solution seems to be to argue that the incident photon is only deterministic on average. In particular, if it has an x probability distribution over a certain length (called a wavelength), one does not know the precise time at which it hits “ x ” the medium interface. In such a situation, there is time uncertainty which allows all three momenta to be compared at the same x . This, however, leads to a major consequence, namely that so-called deterministic motion associated with constant p is deterministic on average, but contains repeated pockets of x probability distributions such that time is not deterministic within. We try to examine these ideas in this note.

Energy/Particle Number and Determinism

Consider a photon moving in the positive x direction which hits a medium interface existing at x . In the deterministic scenario of Newtonian mechanics, the photon moves according to $x=ct$ (assume a vacuum) so a given x (barrier position) is associated with a precise time t . After that time the photon may either reflect OR refract, but it then exists in a different time range. Thus one should be able to compare quantities in the first time range with quantities (information) in the second to see if there exists conservation. In the case of energy and particle number, this applies. There is one incident photon with energy E . If it reflects, then there is one reflected photon with energy E . If it refracts, there is one refracted photon with energy E . If one thinks in terms of probability i.e. “ a ” to reflect and $1-a$ to refract, then before there is one incident photon and after $a+1-a=1$. A main point we make is that one may compare the incident photon with a single possible outcome. This, however, gives no information about the probability to reflect versus that to refract.

Momentum and a Problem with Determinism

Energy and particle number are not the only information in the problem. Momentum is also present and it is important as it is linked to the physical impulse a photon may impart when striking a foil. Using the deterministic argument given in the above section, one may try to compare the incident photon with either the reflected OR refracted. This is where problems occur. A single incident photon has momentum p , while a reflected one has momentum $-p$. A single incident photon has momentum p while a single refracted one has momentum $p_2=n_2p$ with $n_1=1$ where n is the index of refraction. For $n_2>n_1$, $p_2>p_1$. If one only had reflection one might argue that just like a classical ball, the second medium allows for momentum conservation, but with refraction occurring as well matters are not so simple. In fact, it seems a comparison of the incident photon with only the reflected or only the refracted leads to problems.

One might suggest considering all three momenta p , $-p$ and p_2 at the “same time”, but this violates determinism. The incident photon cannot exist at the same time as either the reflected or refracted, although they all exist at the same “ x ” the barrier medium (up to a width Δx which is the interaction range).

Principle 1

It seems that in order to consider all three momenta together, one must give up the notion of determinism. This, however, is a major assumption because it suggests that Newton’s $x=p/m t$ only holds on average. There must be at least a length range w (call this a wavelength) for which the position of a particle is given by probability distribution i.e. time is removed. Given the translationally invariant nature of a medium, this wavelength probability distribution should be repeated. The point is that if there is a probability distribution near x the barrier point, then one does not know exactly at what time the incident photon is at x . Thus there is also probability for either the reflected or refracted photon to exist at x . Since one is dealing with probabilities at x , one should also include the probability that one has either a reflected or refracted photon. These are incorporated as weights of the x -probability distribution Thus an x distribution breaks

determinism, but allows one to compare all three momenta at the same x point and ultimately find the probabilities to reflect and refract given an incident weight.

Probability at x

We argue above that a free particle moving in a medium is deterministic (i.e. $x=p/m t$) only on average. We suggest there exist a set of repeated lengths (wavelengths) each with the same x probability distribution and hence an uncertainty of time within. Thus one cannot say that an incident photon hits x (barrier position) at a precise t . This means that with such an uncertainty one may consider the probabilistic reflection and refraction photons together with the incident one. These should create a probabilistic balance. It is clear that p , $-p$ and p_2 are all different and are linked with different physical impulses, but if there is probability in x then an average impulse is not simply related to p , but to p times a probability weight. Thus one may suggest the equation at $x=0$:

$$A_1 p - p B_1 = C_1 p_2 \quad ((1))$$

where A_1 may be arbitrarily fixed, but B_1 and C_1 are completely unknown.

It should also be noted that for x not equal to zero, there is a function of x over a length (wavelength) which represents an x -probability distribution. What are the properties of this function other than that it is periodic? Does the same function apply to all p values? How is a real x -probability function compatible with $x= p/m t$? We will examine these questions, but first we wish to present a second equation.

In ((1)) A_1, B_1, C_1 are the weights of this x -probability function which is taken to be 1 at $x=0$. Thus one might suggest a second equation balancing probability at $x=0$ i.e.

$$A_1 + B_1 = C_1 \quad ((2))$$

As an aside, one may note that if A_1 (which may be arbitrarily fixed) is taken to be positive and C_1 positive and less than A_1 , then B_1 must be negative.

Given the two equations ((1)) and ((2)), one may solve for B_1 and C_1 in terms of A_1 which is arbitrary. Thus momentum considerations with non-determinism allow one to solve for the probabilities of reflection and refraction in terms of the arbitrary A_1 . These probabilities may be measured experimentally.

Given ((1)) and ((2)) one may ask: What about the conservation of energy and particle number i.e. the deterministic conservation equation. It is also physical and must exist. Given that B_1 may be negative, one cannot use ((1)) as a conservation of energy equation even though $E=|p|c$. For example, one may write ((1)) as: $A_1 E/c = E/c B_1 + C_1 E/c_2$ with A_1 and C_1 positive and B_1 negative, this is not a conservation of energy/particle number equation. One may, however, combine ((1)) and ((2)) i.e. multiply them together to yield:

$$A_1 A_1 p - B_1 B_1 p = C_1 C_1 p_2 \quad ((3))$$

In ((3)), A_1 , B_1 and C_1 are guaranteed to be positive. Thus:

$$A_1 E/c = B_1 E/c + C_1 E/c^2 \quad ((4)) \text{ follows.}$$

In such a case, one may identify A_1 , B_1 and C_1 as intensities/fluxes associated with the incident, reflected and refracted photons where intensity is defined as:

$$\text{Intensity} = \text{number of photons} * E * \text{speed of light} \quad ((5))$$

Thus the probabilistic approach associated with momentum leads to the deterministic result of energy conservation.

The x-Probability Distribution

We now consider the questions regarding the x-probability function. We argue it should be periodic with a periodic length called a wavelength, but is this wavelength p dependent? Furthermore, if there is a probability distribution in x , how is this compatible with each x point carrying the same weight $x = p/m t$ for constant p ?

We first note that the two continuity equations ((1)) and ((2)), if cast in the form of the continuity of a single function and its derivative suggest that:

$$\text{Periodic function } (px) \quad ((6))$$

Thus there is a dynamic feature to the probability distribution. This still leaves the question of the relationship with $x=p/m t$ and introduces another question: What does one do about the direction of p ? If a particle moves on average with $x=p/m t$, but there is a probability distribution associated with x , then at one time instant and another there should be two probability distributions. These must be combined, however, to indicate two different time instances, hence one would not simply add the two. The two distributions should have the same form, but perhaps be shifted. This suggests a two dimensional form which maps into a constant i.e.

$$\text{Probability} = \exp(ipx)$$

In the case of reflection/refraction problem one may give weights to $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. A_1, B_1, C_1 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we use Newtonian determinism i.e. $x= p/m t$ to examine the problem of reflection/refraction of photons in the macroscopic classical world with the medium interface existing at x . This means the incident photon arrives at x at a precise time t and either the reflected or refracted photon exists at x at a later time. One may apply conservation of energy or particle number between the incident photon and either the reflected OR refracted photon. For instance there is one incident photon with energy E . If it reflects, there is one reflected photon

with energy E . Momentum, however, is also an important piece of information in the problem, associated with physical impulse, and it does not have this property. There is one incident with momentum p and if it reflects, there is one reflected photon with momentum $-p$. If it refracts, there is one photon with momentum p_2 ? Where is conservation of momentum in the refraction case? Thus we argue that one may have to consider all three momenta p , $-p$, p_2 together, but how is this possible if the incident photon does not exist at the same time as the reflected/refracted one? One way to do this is to assume one does not know exactly when the incident photon arrives at x the interface point, but this violates $x = p/m t$. One may argue that $x = p/m t$ on average and that really there exists an x -probability distribution over a length called a wavelength. In such a region one does not have the deterministic $x = p/m t$, but rather probabilities. Given that there are probabilities to reflect and refract, one may incorporate these probabilities as weights of the x -probability distribution and create two continuity equations:

$$A_1 + B_1 = C_1 \quad (\text{incident+reflected=refracted}) \quad \text{and} \quad A_1 p - p B_1 = p_2 C_1$$

This allows one to solve for B_1, C_1 in terms of A_1 . One may see that if $A_1 > 0$, $C_1 > 0$ and $A_1 > C_1$ then $B_1 < 0$, so the second equation cannot be equivalent to a conservation of energy equation. Yet such a conservation equation should exist. It may be created by multiplying the two equations together as shown in the note.

A main feature that arises is that in breaking determinism even a particle with constant p has repeated x -probability distributions. We argue in the note that it is governed by the probability form $\exp(ipx)$, while at the same exhibiting on average $x = p/m t$.